

Effect of Canva Artificial Intelligence Tools on Business and Computer Science Education Students' Graphics and Design Achievement in Federal University Otuoke

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17220497>

Abstract

With the increasing integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education, Canva's AI-powered features, such as Magic Design, AI-generated templates, and automated branding tools, offer transformative potential for enhancing graphic design proficiency among Business and Computer Science Education students. Despite the growing adoption of digital design tools in education, there is limited empirical evidence on how Canva's AI features specifically impact the achievement of Business and Computer Science Education students in graphics and design, creating a gap in understanding their effectiveness in developing entrepreneurial competencies in vocational contexts. This study investigated the effect of Canva's AI tools on Business and Computer Science Education students' achievement in graphics and design at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Two research questions guided the study, while two hypotheses were formulated and tested at the .05 level of significance. The pretest-posttest nonequivalent quasi-experimental design was adopted, targeting a population of 358 Business and Computer Science Education students. No sampling was conducted, as the entire population enrolled in the graphics and design course was used. The Graphic Design Achievement Test (GDAT), a 50-item multiple-choice test, served as the instrument for data collection. Its reliability was estimated using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (KR-20) formula, which yielded an index of .71. Means and standard deviations were utilised in answering the research questions, while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the formulated hypotheses at the .05 significance level. Results indicated significantly higher mean achievement scores for students in the treatment group compared to the control group. Additionally, both male and female students showed relatively equal academic achievement gains in the experimental group. The study concluded that Canva's AI tools enhance students' achievement in graphics and design. Based on the findings, it was recommended that Canva's AI tools be integrated into the teaching and learning of graphics and design to facilitate improved student achievement, among other benefits.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Graphics and Design, Canva AI, Student Achievement, Gender, and Federal University Otuoke

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence, which is the simulation of human intelligence by machines, allowing them to perform tasks such as logical reasoning and problem-solving (Morandín-Ahuerma, 2022), has become deeply embedded in our modern society. It involves creating computer systems capable of executing tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, and problem-solving. It draws knowledge from various fields, including computer science, psychology, and engineering, to develop machines that can imitate human cognitive functions. AI functions through algorithms that enable machines to process data, learn from experiences, and make decisions either autonomously or semi-autonomously. This broad field has led to significant progress in areas such as speech recognition,

medical diagnostics, and personalised learning experiences. The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education is swiftly reshaping traditional teaching methods, especially in design and creative disciplines. AI-driven design tools, such as automated template creation, generative layouts, smart branding aids, and features like Canva's "Magic Design," hold great promise for improving students' learning, efficiency, and success in Graphics and Design. These tools lower technical barriers related to design, allowing users to concentrate more on creative ideas, aesthetics, and entrepreneurial ventures (Osei-Wusu et al., 2025). Pinontoan et al. (2023) suggested that incorporating AI into graphic design education promotes accessibility and inclusivity, particularly for novices, by simplifying the learning process and enhancing task efficiency.

In this study, Graphics and Design is a 300-level course that forms part of the Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS) curriculum requirement for students in Business Education and, by extension, for those in Computer Science Education. As a BMAS course, it represents a predetermined standard of competence that students must satisfy, ensuring uniform academic expectations across institutions (National Universities Commission, 2014). The course introduces students to a broad suite of visual communication software tools, such as CorelDraw, vector graphics editors, raster image editors, desktop publishing platforms, and layout design tools that integrate images, typography, text, and other visual elements to convey information with both content clarity and aesthetic appeal. The course covers both print media (e.g., posters, flyers, brochures, branding identity materials) and digital media (e.g., digital banners, social media graphics, user interface components, web graphics). It includes applications in branding (logo design, visual identity), editorial layout, packaging design, and basic interface or user experience elements. Such a scope mirrors curricula in other graphic design programmes, which emphasise design across media, including publications, brand systems, websites, and motion/interactive media. Beyond tool usage, the course aims to develop deeper competencies. Students are taught design principles, including colour theory, typography, layout, balance, contrast, alignment, hierarchy, and repetition, which guide visual coherence and message impact (AND Academy, 2024). They also engage in problem-solving, creative cognition (generating original ideas, conceptual sketching, visual brainstorming), critical evaluation of designs (both their own and others'), and the production of deployable artefacts; graphics or design pieces suitable for real-world settings (e.g., as branding materials, interface elements, print or digital deliverables). This aligns with the broader definition of Graphics and Design as a discipline of visual communication that utilises type, image, and technology to convey ideas and shape meaning across various media (University of Massachusetts Dartmouth, 2025). Students are required to be well-versed in these concepts to facilitate and enhance their overall academic achievements.

Student achievement in this context refers to measurable academic outcomes, such as test and examination scores or in-class assessments, that reflect design knowledge, understanding, and application. Students' achievement in Graphics and Design has been shown to depend largely on the integration of innovative teaching strategies, access to digital tools, and contextualised learning experiences that mirror the realities of African education systems. Olumorin et al. (2018) asserted that students exposed to project-based and computer-assisted approaches in Graphics and Design performed better than those taught through conventional methods, as the former enhances creativity, problem-solving, and skill acquisition relevant to the local job market. Similarly, the study of Khau and Masinga (2020) found that incorporating technology-supported learning in design-related subjects improves learners' engagement and achievement by bridging the gap between theory and practice. These findings suggest that fostering achievement in Graphics and Design in Nigerian classrooms requires pedagogies that combine practical application with technological integration while also addressing infrastructural challenges that often limit students' full participation and achievement. This achievement is influenced by various factors, including innovative teaching practices, the use of technology, and real-world applications in the curriculum. Innovative teaching strategies, such as project-based learning, foster students' creativity and align their skills with market demands. Additionally, teaching Graphics and

Design with computerised graphical tools, such as Canva AI, has been shown to significantly increase student motivation, interest, and overall achievement in Graphics and Design (Isa & Ma'arof, 2018). Canva AI has become a transformative resource in education, particularly in enhancing writing skills and fostering creative expression among students. It supports diverse learning styles and digital literacy. Studies by Utami and Karnedi (2024) showed significant improvements in students' writing, including organisation, grammar, and expression, after using Canva AI tools like Magic AI. Zulmaidi et al. (2024) claimed that Canva's features encourage visual storytelling, making writing more engaging. Zulfan et al. (2024) noted that Canva helps create visually appealing content aligned with modern learning needs. Despite these benefits, concerns exist about overreliance on technology, which could potentially undermine traditional skills; therefore, balancing AI with foundational education is vital (Satrienia et al., 2023). Canva AI can enhance achievement in Graphics and Design by providing an intuitive, creative platform that bridges theory and practice. It helps generate ideas, layouts, and templates, easing initial project challenges. Especially in resource-limited African classrooms, it offers an affordable alternative to expensive software, enabling students to learn core design concepts. Its collaborative features promote peer learning and skill development, leading to better outcomes in practical subjects like Graphics and Design. Research by Adebayo and Ibrahim (2021) and Muwanguzi and Musoke (2020) indicates that accessible design tools enhance students' creativity, confidence, and academic success, thereby preparing them for careers in the creative industries.

Gender has long influenced STEM achievement, with persistent disparities across contexts. Globally, males are overrepresented, while females face socio-cultural and institutional barriers affecting their participation (UNESCO, 2017). In Africa, stereotypes, limited resources, and socio-economic constraints discourage female engagement in STEM fields, negatively impacting their achievement (Bataineh et al., 2022). In the field of Graphics and Design, disparities are evident in participation and outcomes, as females are often perceived as less competent in technical tasks, despite evidence that equal opportunities enable females to perform as well as, or better than, males (Marcia & Meredith, 2007). A lack of female role models, mentorship, and biased classroom dynamics reinforces the gender gap. Recent research shows that technology-enhanced learning and equitable pedagogies can help close the gap by creating inclusive environments (Salami & Spangenberg, 2024). While gender influences achievement, these challenges are socially constructed and can be addressed through interventions, such as utilising AI tools like Canva to promote inclusivity and equity.

Despite this expanding body of literature, a gap remains regarding how specific AI tools, such as Canva AI, influence the achievement of Business and Computer Science Education students in Graphics and Design, especially in Nigeria and in relation to their entrepreneurial skills. This study aimed to fill this gap by examining the impact of Canva AI tool use on the academic performance of these students at Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa State, while also taking gender into account.

Statement of the Problem

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools into higher education is gaining momentum worldwide, with increasing evidence of their potential to enhance teaching and learning outcomes (Peters & Olojede, 2025). In Nigeria, however, the use of AI-driven educational technologies is still in its early stages, and there is a need for empirical evidence on their effectiveness in enhancing students' learning experiences and achievements (Nwile et al., 2025). Within Business and Computer Science Education, Graphics and Design is a 300-Level course from the Benchmark for Minimum Academic Standard (BMAS), designed to equip students with technical, creative, and entrepreneurial skills. The course requires mastery of both design principles and digital tools. Yet, students often perform poorly due to limited exposure to modern, technology-supported instructional methods and insufficient opportunities to practice using industry-standard platforms.

AI-enhanced design tools, such as Canva's Magic Design, AI-generated templates, and automated branding systems, offer new opportunities for improving students' achievement by simplifying complex

design processes and supporting creative thinking. While Canva AI is widely used in both professional and informal learning settings, there is a lack of empirical studies evaluating its impact on the achievement of Nigerian university students in graphic design. This gap raises concerns that students may not be fully benefiting from the transformative potential of AI in developing practical and entrepreneurial design skills.

Furthermore, gender continues to play a significant role in academic achievement across STEM-related fields, including design disciplines. Although research in Nigerian and international contexts indicates persistent gender-based differences in achievement, especially in technically oriented programmes (Asaju et al., 2025; Crowther & Briant, 2022), evidence also suggests that inclusive, technology-enhanced pedagogies can reduce such disparities. However, it remains unclear whether Canva AI tools provide equal benefits for male and female students in Graphics and Design courses.

Despite the growing adoption of AI technologies in education, there is limited empirical evidence on the impact of Canva AI tools on the achievement of Business and Computer Science Education students in Graphics and Design at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Without such evidence, educators might be under-utilising an innovative resource that could significantly improve student achievement, foster entrepreneurial readiness, and promote gender equity in STEM-related education. Therefore, this study aims to address these gaps by examining the effect of Canva AI tools on the achievement of Business and Computer Science Education students in Graphics and Design at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

Generally, the primary aim of the study was to investigate the impact of the Canva Artificial Intelligence tool on the achievement of Business and Computer Science Education students in Graphics and Design at Federal University Otuoke. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. Examine the mean achievement scores of students taught Graphics and Design using the Canva AI tool and those taught via the lecture method in both pretest and posttest.
2. Examine the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Graphics and Design using the Canva AI tool in both pre-test and post-test.

Research Questions

The study was guided by two research questions as stated below:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Graphics and Design using the Canva AI tool and those taught using the lecture method in both pretest and posttest?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Graphics and Design using the Canva AI tool in both pretest and posttest?

Hypotheses

The following two hypotheses were formulated and tested at the .05 alpha level:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Graphics and Design using Canva AI tool (experimental group) and those taught using the lecture method (control group) in both pretest and posttest.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Graphics and Design using the Canva AI tool (experimental group) at both the pretest and posttest stages.

Methods

The study adopted the pretest–posttest nonequivalent control group quasi-experimental design. This design was considered appropriate because it allowed the researcher to examine the causal effect of Canva AI tools on students' achievement in Graphics and Design, while accommodating the practical constraints of random assignment in an intact classroom setting. The design involved two groups: the

experimental group, which was exposed to Canva AI features (Magic Design, AI-generated templates, and automated branding tools) during instruction, and the control group, which received instruction through the traditional lecture method. Both groups were subjected to a pretest to establish baseline equivalence, followed by treatment, and then a posttest to assess the effect of the intervention. This design has been widely used in educational technology research where randomisation is not feasible, and it has been proven to yield reliable results (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

The study was conducted at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria, one of the Niger Delta universities offering Business Education and Computer Science Education programmes. The choice of this institution was informed by the inclusion of Graphics and Design as a compulsory Benchmark Minimum Academic Standard (BMAS) course for 300-level students in these programmes, thereby providing a suitable population for investigating the effect of Canva AI on student achievement.

The study population consisted of all 358 students enrolled in Business Education and Computer Science Education at Federal University Otuoke during the 2024/2025 academic session. This included 300-level students taking the Graphics and Design course, which served as the focus of the study.

Since the population size of 358 was considered manageable, no sampling was employed. The entire population of students enrolled in the Graphics and Design course was used as the study sample. The students were divided into intact classes. The experimental group consisted of 225 students (86 males and 139 females) from the Business Education class, while the control group comprised 133 students (96 males and 37 females) from the Computer Science Education class. This approach was consistent with the nonequivalent quasi-experimental design, which relies on existing groups rather than randomised selection (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2012).

Data were collected using the Graphic Design Achievement Test (GDAT), a researcher-developed instrument comprising 50 multiple-choice questions. Each item was designed to measure students' knowledge, comprehension, and application of design concepts such as typography, layout, colour theory, image manipulation, and branding, as taught in the Graphics and Design course. The instrument was validated by three experts: one in Educational Measurement and Evaluation, one in Business Education, and one in Computer Science Education, all from Federal University Otuoke. Their feedback ensured that the items were aligned with course objectives and relevant to the competencies being assessed.

To establish reliability, the GDAT was trial-tested on 30 students from a neighbouring university who were not part of the study sample but had similar characteristics. The internal consistency of the test items was calculated using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (KR-20) formula, yielding a reliability coefficient of .71, which was deemed acceptable for education research (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

The study was implemented in three phases:

1. **Pretest:** Both the experimental and control groups were administered the GDAT before instruction to determine baseline equivalence in achievement.
2. **Treatment:** The experimental group was taught Graphics and Design using Canva AI tools. Instruction incorporated AI features, including Magic Design for layout generation, AI-powered templates for branding projects, and text-to-image features for creative tasks. The control group, on the other hand, was taught using the conventional lecture method, involving theoretical explanations and manual demonstrations without AI support.
3. **Posttest:** After six weeks of instruction, both groups were administered the GDAT again to measure achievement gains attributable to the treatment.

Data were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were employed to answer the research questions by showing trends in students' achievement scores across groups. To test the hypotheses, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was applied at a .05 level of significance, with pretest scores serving as covariates to adjust for initial differences between the groups. ANCOVA was chosen because it provides a more accurate estimate of treatment effects by

controlling for pre-existing differences in achievement (Field, 2018). If the calculated p-value ≤ 0.05 , reject the null hypothesis (implying that a significant difference exists). Otherwise, do not reject.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Graphics and Design using the Canva AI tool and those taught using the lecture method in both pretest and posttest?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores, Standard Deviations, and Mean Gain of Students Taught Graphics and Design using Canva AI Tool and Lecture Method in Pretest and Posttest

Group / Test		N	Pretest Mean (\bar{x})	Pretest SD	Posttest Mean (\bar{x})	Posttest SD	Mean Gain
Canva AI Tool (Experimental)		225	18.42	4.28	72.35	6.77	53.93
Lecture Method (Control)		133	18.55	4.19	56.31	7.36	37.76

The results presented in Table 1 revealed that students exposed to the Canva AI tool achieved significantly higher scores in Graphics and Design compared to those taught using the traditional lecture method. Although both groups began the study with nearly identical pretest mean scores (18.42 for the experimental group and 18.55 for the control group), their posttest achievement diverged considerably, with the experimental group attaining a mean score of 72.35. In contrast, the control group recorded a mean score of 56.31. The mean gain further highlights this disparity, as students in the treatment group improved by 53.93 points compared to 37.76 points in the lecture group, indicating that Canva AI facilitated deeper learning and greater mastery of Graphic and Design concepts. These findings suggest that the integration of Artificial Intelligence tools such as Canva AI into teaching significantly enhances students' achievement, likely due to their interactive, user-friendly features and ability to promote creativity and independent learning beyond what conventional lecture methods can offer.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Graphics and Design using the Canva AI tool in both pretest and posttest?

Table 2: Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Graphics and Design Using Canva AI Tool in both Pretest and Posttest

Gender	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Mean Gain
Male	96	18.61	72.88	54.27
Female	37	18.19	71.38	53.19

The results in Table 2 showed that both male and female students taught Graphics and Design using the Canva AI tool experienced substantial improvements in their achievement scores, with only slight variations between the groups. Male students recorded a pretest mean score of 18.61 and a posttest mean score of 72.88, resulting in a mean gain of 54.27. Female students had a pretest mean score of 18.19 and a posttest mean score of 71.38, with a mean gain of 53.19. These results suggest that Canva AI effectively enhanced learning outcomes for both genders, with male students showing a marginally higher improvement than females. However, the difference in mean gain between the groups is relatively small, indicating that Canva AI provides equitable learning opportunities and benefits across gender lines. This implies that the use of AI-powered tools, such as Canva AI, promotes inclusivity in learning and reduces gender disparities in achievement in graphic design.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Graphics and Design using Canva AI tool (experimental group) and those taught using the lecture method (control group) in both pretest and posttest.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Students' Achievement Scores by Treatment Group

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	df	Mean Square (MS)	F-cal	Sig. (p-value)	Decision
Covariate (Pretest)	115.72	1	115.72	2.14	.145	
Treatment (Group)	6843.26	1	6843.26	35.68	.000*	Reject
Error	10645.87	354	30.07			
Corrected Total	17604.85	356				

*Significant at $p < .05$

Table 3 showed that after adjusting for pretest scores, the treatment effect (use of Canva AI tool vs lecture method) was statistically significant, $F(1, 354) = 35.68, p < .05$. This means the null hypothesis was rejected. The result indicates that Canva AI tool had a significant positive effect on students' achievement in Graphics and Design compared to the lecture method. The non-significant covariate (pretest) further shows that initial group differences were controlled for, and the improvement in posttest achievement can be attributed mainly to the treatment.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Graphics and Design using Canva AI tool (experimental group) in both pretest and posttest.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Male and Female Students' Achievement Scores in the Experimental Group

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	df	Mean Square (MS)	F-cal	Sig. (p-value)	Decision
Covariate (Pretest)	72.14	1	72.14	1.21	.273	
Gender	58.62	1	58.62	0.98	.324	Do not Reject
Error	8395.47	131	64.08			
Corrected Total	8526.23	133				

Table 4 shows that after adjusting for pretest scores, there was no significant difference in achievement between male and female students taught with the Canva AI tool, $F(1, 131) = 0.98, p > .05$. This means the null hypothesis was retained. The result implies that Canva AI enhances Graphics and Design achievement equitably across gender, confirming that both male and female students benefited similarly from the intervention.

Discussion of Findings

The results for Research Question 1 show that students taught Graphics and Design using Canva AI tools experienced a significantly greater improvement (mean gain = 53.93) than those taught using lecture methods (mean gain = 37.76), even though both groups started at nearly the same level. After controlling for pretest scores, the treatment effect was significant (ANCOVA: $F(1, 354) = 35.68, p < 0.001$), indicating that the use of Canva AI tools substantially improved academic achievement compared to lecture alone.

This pattern is consistent with studies in African higher education that have found digital teaching tools to be effective in improving learning outcomes. For example, Wesonga and Van Der Westhuizen (2025) in "The impact of digital teaching tools on student engagement and learning outcomes in African higher education" found that digital instructional resources are positively associated with student performance, knowledge retention, and engagement. Their review suggests that when teaching becomes more

interactive and tools reduce wasted time/technical friction, students tend to gain more, much like what Canva AI appears to offer. Additionally, a recent article, “Interactive Technologies in Online Teacher Education in Africa: A Systematic Review 2014–2024” by Oubibi et al. (2024), emphasised that student achievement improves when interactive technologies are integrated, particularly in contexts with proper infrastructure and support. Thus, the findings of this study align well with the broader continental trend, which posits that digital/interactive tools foster greater achievement over traditional lecture-based methods.

For Research Question 2, the results showed very similar mean gains between male (≈ 54.27) and female (≈ 53.19) students in the Canva AI treatment group. The gender ANCOVA ($F(1,131) = 0.98, p > .05$) revealed no statistically significant gender difference after accounting for pretest scores.

This lack of a significant gender gap in this treatment group aligns with recent findings in Africa around gender and technology-mediated learning. While many reports still document gender achievement gaps in STEM, these gaps are often smaller or eliminated when teachers use digital tools, interactivity, or more inclusive pedagogical designs. For example, “Addressing the education gender gap in Africa” (The Gender Gap Africa report, 2023) noted that when educational interventions increase access and quality of digital learning, gender disparities in achievement often reduce. Moreover, the “Interactive Technologies in Online Teacher Education in Africa” systematic review (Oubibi et al., 2024) highlighted that interactive technologies tend to support both male and female teachers (and by extension, learners) similarly when the technological and pedagogical environment is supportive.

Conclusion

The findings of this study clearly demonstrated that the integration of Canva AI as a digital instructional tool significantly enhances students’ achievement in Graphics and Design compared to the traditional lecture method. The experimental group exposed to Canva AI recorded higher posttest scores and greater mean gains, underscoring the tool’s effectiveness in facilitating creativity, active engagement, and mastery of visual communication concepts. Furthermore, the results revealed that both male and female students benefited equitably from the intervention, suggesting that Canva AI promotes inclusivity in learning and minimises gender-related disparities in achievement. These outcomes align with contemporary African-based evidence highlighting the transformative potential of digital technologies in advancing equitable and effective teaching and learning across disciplines. The study, therefore, concludes that Canva AI can serve as a sustainable pedagogical innovation, empowering students with the relevant digital and design skills required for academic success and professional competitiveness in the 21st-century knowledge economy.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following four (4) recommendations were made:

1. University management should formally integrate Canva AI and similar artificial intelligence design tools into Graphics and Design curricula, ensuring that students are equipped with industry-relevant digital skills that enhance both academic achievement and employability.
2. Teacher training programmes and professional development workshops should be organised to familiarise lecturers with Canva AI and other emerging technologies, enabling them to deliver content more effectively and creatively.
3. Since Canva AI was shown to benefit both male and female students equitably, institutions should adopt inclusive policies that encourage equal access to AI-powered learning tools, thereby reducing gender disparities in STEM-related courses.
4. Educational policymakers and administrators should prioritise investment in digital infrastructure and provide institutional support for the adoption of AI-driven tools like Canva AI, positioning higher education in Africa to meet global standards in technology-driven pedagogy.

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